

Environmental Impacts of Sand Mining in Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (1990-2024)

Ubongabasi Ebenezer Israel

Department of History and International Studies, University of Uyo, Nigeria

Abstract

As the most extracted natural resources on earth, the unchecked and unregulated removal of sand from rivers and streambeds have generated ecological implications that fall heaviest on communities in the developing world. In Nigeria, where the Minerals and Mining Act of 2007 is inconsistently enforced and urban construction demand has grown rapidly since the late twentieth century, riverine sand dredging has expanded far beyond the capacity of affected waterways to recover. This paper examines the environmental impacts of sand mining in Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, between 1990 and 2024, with particular attention on the Mkpok brook, the primary site of extraction. Drawing on oral interviews with sand miners, dredger operators, and community leaders, supplemented by newspaper reports, environmental assessments, and published scholarly literature, the paper traces the factors that drove commercial sand extraction into Onna, the social and economic mechanisms through which it expanded into a large-scale dredging operation, as well as the cumulative physical and ecological consequences it imposed on the area's landscape, water systems, agricultural land, and infrastructure. The findings reveal that the escalation of dredging activity was enabled by the institutional failure of Akwa Ibom State regulatory bodies, the compliance of community elders who accepted informal payments in lieu of licensing, and the entry of non-indigene operators from neighbouring states who bore no long-term stake in the communities they exploited. The paper concludes by recommending enforceable post-mining restoration frameworks and stronger community land rights over communal waterways.

Keywords: *Sand, Infrastructure, Onna, Minerals, Dredging, Environmental Degradation.*

Suggested citation: Israel, U.E. (2026). Environmental Impacts of Sand Mining in Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (1990-2024). *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 3(7), 17-27. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2026.3(7).02

Introduction

Sand is the most extracted solid material on earth and the second most consumed natural resource after water. It is used daily for building, construction and so many other domestic and commercial purposes (Leal Filho et al., 2021). Global demand for sand and gravel has tripled over the past two decades, reaching an estimated fifty billion tonnes per year (UNEP, 2022). This increase in volume is primarily driven by rapid urbanization, population growth, and the construction industry's heavy reliance on concrete as its primary building material (UNEP, 2022). However, the unchecked and unregulated removal of sand from rivers, streambeds, and coastal areas has generated one of the most consequential but least discussed environmental crises. This hinges on the fact that the pace

of sand extraction far exceeds the rate at which natural processes replenish its sandy sediments. While the ecological costs which ranges from riverbank erosion and aquatic habitat loss to contaminated water bodies and degraded farmlands have been well established by scholars like Marius Dan Gavriletea (Gavriletea, 2017), the underlying factors that gives rise to unregulated sand extraction remain largely under-discussed with no serious response from government. In sub-Saharan Africa, where regulatory capacity on sand mining is weakest and urban construction demand is rapidly rising, these costs fall disproportionately on rural and peri-urban communities that depend on rivers and land for their livelihoods (Torres et al., 2017).

Sand mining operations, many of which are illegal and operating without environmental oversight, have proliferated across the Nigeria's coastal areas. These activities are invigorated by the increasing construction demands of growing urban populations and enabled by the weak enforcement policies of the Minerals and Mining Act of 2007 (Aliu et al., 2022). In Akwa Ibom State, this problem is particularly serious as studies conducted across the state have found that sand mining permit acquisition is widely ignored among operators. Government-mandated monitoring agencies on their part have also failed to visit active sites, and that vast stretches of agricultural land have been converted into borrow pits and wastelands with no remediation (Abraham et al., 2021). One of the areas affected by unregulated sand mining is Onna Local Government Area. The unregulated dredging of the Mkpok brook which intensified from the 1990s, has for over three decades produced measurable damage to the area's landscape, water systems, infrastructure, and farming communities. Against this backdrop, this paper seeks to examine the history of sand mining in Onna LGA from 1990 to 2024, tracing the causes that drove commercialized extraction, the course through which it expanded and escalated, and the consequences it has left on the surrounding environment and the people.

The Land of Onna

Onna Local Government Area is in the southern part of Akwa Ibom State. It is one of the thirty-one LGAs that make up the state which was created on 23 September 1987 from the former Cross River State (Akwa Ibom State Government, n.d.). The name Onna is itself an acronym that is drawn from the initials of the four predominant clans that make up the area; Oniong, Nnung Ndem, Awa Afaha, and Asuna Nung Oku (Offong, personal communication, April 19, 2026). Its administrative headquarter is located at Abat town, and its principal settlements include Awa, Iquita, Nung Ndem, and Oniong (Offong, personal communication, April 19, 2026).

Geographically, the local government is bounded to the east by Eket, to the west by Mkpato Enin, and to the south by the Atlantic Ocean. This geographical positioning gives it a transitional ecological atmosphere which connects the inland freshwater and riparian zones of Akwa Ibom's hinterland with the coastal and estuarine margins of the Niger Delta. The Ibibio-speaking people of Onna are one of the principal ethnic communities of the state. Onna has an ecological profile that consists of a tropical monsoon climate, dense forest vegetation of the Cross-Niger transition type, and a landscape that is characterized by fertile soils, thick riverine cover, and a network of brooks and seasonal streams. From 2002 to 2024, Onna has lost a large portion of its humid primary forest, making up 0.70% of its total tree cover loss in the same time period. Total area of humid primary forest in Onna decreased by 2.0% in this time period (Global Forest Watch, n.d.).

Onna is among the oil-producing local government areas of Akwa Ibom State. It hosts active petroleum operations in communities such as Ukpana, Akpabom, and Ikwe, and serve as the site of the Ikwe-Onna modular refinery project that was developed in partnership with the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (Harry et al., 2022). This industrial sector has co-existed, often uneasily, with the predominantly agrarian and fishing-based livelihoods that has historically

sustained majority of Onna's population due to pollutions that the oil company injects into the farmlands and streams of the people. Before the intensification of both oil extraction and sand mining from the late 1980s and 1990s onward, the communities in Onna depended primarily on subsistence and small-scale commercial farming. The array of crops that were cultivated across the area included yam, cassava, cocoyam, plantain, and vegetables.

One of the fluvial features of Onna is the Mkpok brook. This is a freshwater stream that drains portions of the LGA and feeds into the hydrological network of the Niger Delta coastal plain. Before commercial sand dredging operations began, the Mkpok brook functioned as an ecologically productive waterway. Its riparian zone supports a range of aquatic species and provided communities with fish, freshwater, and irrigable land along its banks. The vegetation corridor that flanks the brook also serve as a natural barrier against erosion, thus, stabilizing the surrounding agricultural land and moderating the hydrological behaviour of the stream during seasonal rainfall. An environmental impact assessment carried out on oil-producing communities in Onna and neighbouring LGAs confirmed that the area's water bodies, and creek systems were vital to the subsistence economy of the local populations prior to the escalation of extractive activities (Harry et al., 2022).

The Genesis of Sand Mining in Onna

Sand mining as a commercial activity in Nigeria predates the existence of Akwa Ibom State. The practice is believed to have begun in the 1960s in Bariga Local Government Area of Lagos State, where rapid urban growth generated early construction demand that made riverine sand extraction a commercially viable livelihood for local operators (Right for Education, 2024). From that Lagos origin point, the practice spread across the country's river systems and coastal areas over the following decades. By the time Akwa Ibom State was created on 23 September 1987, sand mining had already established itself as an informal but economically viable sector across Nigeria's southern states, with mining operators who were experienced enough in identifying accessible waterways close to growing urban centres.

The creation of Akwa Ibom State was the single most consequential event in the origin of sand mining in Onna. When Uyo was designated as the new state capital, it became an immediate magnet for government investment in administrative buildings, roads, staff quarters, schools, and residential estates. Construction that had not previously existed in Uyo at any significant scale began at once and sustained itself through the 1990s as successive administrations invested in the physical infrastructure of the new state. Britannica's profile of Akwa Ibom State confirmed that the inland city of Uyo is the site of a university founded in 1983, and that the state's bigger development trajectory accelerated sharply after its creation, generating huge demand for building materials across its urban core (*Encyclopaedia Britannica*, n.d.). Sand was the most needed of those materials, and the question facing operators who recognized this demand was simply a geographical one. Where were the nearest accessible sandy waterways? Onna Local Government Area provided an immediate answer to that question.

Onna was at proximity to Uyo's construction markets which made tipper lorry transportation economically viable. Its waterways sat within a Niger Delta alluvial geology that deposits the kind of coarse, angular sharp sand that was most prized by the construction industry for concrete and foundation work (Attah et al., 2024). The earliest phase of sand extraction in Onna was on a small-scale level. It was conducted by local young men using canoes, metallic buckets, and hand shovels to remove sand from the shallower sections of the Mkpok brook and sell it directly to tipper lorry operators who transported it to Uyo. The miners usually began their work very early in the morning

around 3 or 4 a.m. when the river tide was relatively calm and easy to navigate (Akpan, personal communication, April 16, 2026).

Traditionally, the mining process relied heavily on manual labour and simple tools like canoes, long wooden poles, buckets, head pans, and short-handled shovels. Each canoe was manned by a two-man team consisting of a paddler and a diver. The paddler's task was to maintain balance and direction of the canoe while the diver went underwater to collect sand. The diver descended into the river with a bucket tied to a rope, using his hands to scoop sand from the riverbed into the bucket (Akpan, personal communication, April 16, 2026). When the bucket was full, he resurfaced, emptied it into the canoe, and dived again. This process was repeated tirelessly up till thirty times and sometimes the diver and the paddler swapped positions until the canoe was filled with wet sand (Akpan, personal communication, April 16, 2026). *Premium Times*, in its 2020 investigative report on sand mining communities in Akwa Ibom, observed this same manual method of sand mining that was still operating in parts of the state appeared to pose less environmental consequences than dredger-based operations (Premium Times, 2020).

Figure 1. A Sand Miner with his boat after Mining

Source: <https://coastalcare.org/2016/04/nigeria-akwa-ibom-illegal-sand-mining-threatens-calabar-itu-mkpok-bridges/> (accessed and retrieved, 14 April 2026).

The transition from this manual form of sand mining to a commercial and mechanized dredging in Onna occurred gradually through the 1990s as operators from neighbouring states identified the Mkpok brook as a good site for sand mining. This period of entry into Akwa Ibom communities was due to the increase in demand for sand and the absence of a regulatory enforcement body across the state (Akpan, 2015). In Onna, the coming of these operators was secured through the informal practice of bribing community elders with gifts of locally brewed alcohol, goat meat, and token cash to gain access to the Mkpok brook without any formal licensing process (Umo, 2016).

The Process of Sand Dredging in Onna

The activities of Sand mining in Onna Local Government Area is carried out almost exclusively through riverbed dredging. This is a process that involves the mechanical extraction of sandy sediment from beneath the surface of the Mkpok brook using motorized suction equipment. Unlike open-pit or quarry mining, which takes place on dry land, dredging is an entirely aquatic

operation. The machines work on the water while the sand comes from beneath the water. The entire process runs continuously for as long as the engine has fuel, and the operator has buyers waiting onshore (Ehirim et al., 2022).

The primary machine used in dredging operations at the Mkpok brook is the jet suction dredger. This machine floats on the surface of the water on a steel or wooden pontoon that serves as its base platform. Mounted on this floating platform are the diesel engine, the water jet pump, and the centrifugal suction pump (Sand Dredgers, n.d.). The water jet pump sends a high-pressure stream of water downward through a suction ladder, which is a long pipe arm that hangs from the front of the pontoon and extends below the waterline to the riverbed. At the end of this suction ladder is the nozzle, which blasts water into the sandy sediment at the bottom of the brook, breaking it apart and suspending it in a sand-water mixture known as slurry. The centrifugal suction pump then draws this slurry upward through the suction pipe and expels it at high pressure along a discharge pipeline made of white PVC or high-density polyethylene piping that runs from the dredger on the water to a stockpile point on the bank (African Land, n.d.). The pipeline can extend for several hundred metres depending on how far the stockpile area is from the water's edge.

Figure 2. Diagram of a Jet Suction Dredger

Source: <https://www.dredgepumpchina.com/jet-suction-dredger/> (accessed and retrieved, 18 April 2026).

The jet suction dredger that is commonly used by small-scale operators in Nigerian river systems is capable of operating at depths between one and twenty-five metres, with the suction ladder adjusted manually or by winch to reach different sediment levels (Sand Dredgers, n.d.). Small-scale units with six-to-eight-inch suction pipe diameters process between fifty and one hundred cubic metres of sandy slurry per hour, while larger fourteen-inch units handle between two hundred and five hundred cubic metres per hour (Sand Pump Machine, n.d.). Entry-level portable dredger units of the type used by operators cost between eight thousand to two hundred and fifteen thousand United States dollars (\$8,000-\$250,000) depending on the engine size and pump capacity (Accio, n.d.). Mid-range units capable of deeper extraction reach prices of between thirty thousand and one hundred thousand dollars (\$30,000-\$100,000). In practice, operators in Onna either purchase cheaper portable units outright, lease equipment from more capitalized principals based in Abia or Imo States, or pool resources across a small group of co-investors to share the cost of a single machine (Aniekan, personal communication, April 14, 2026).

At the site by the riverbank, the sand-water slurry discharges continuously from the end of the pipeline into a growing mound. The water component then drains off naturally through the sandy soil while the sand itself accumulates into a stockpile that grows larger throughout the working day. Once the stockpile has reached a sufficient volume, it is loaded into tipper lorries using a payloader or manually by labourers with shovels. A standard single-axle tipper lorry carries between five and seven tonnes of sand and takes between thirty and forty-five minutes to fill from an established stockpile. A long-body articulated tipper carrying fifteen to twenty tonnes requires between one and two hours to load fully (Adebayo, 2017). On an active site like the Mkpok brook, where thirty-two dredgers operate simultaneously, the combined output of machines running parallel operations is sufficient to keep a continuous queue of lorries loading and departing throughout the day (Moses, 2016).

The operational crew usually consist of a dredge operator who controls the engine, monitors suction depth, and repositions the pontoon to where sand is easier to evacuate as sections of the riverbed can get exhausted after repeated dredging. A pipeline attendant monitors the discharge line for blockages and redirects it as the stockpile grows. One or two general labourers assist with loading, refuelling, and routine maintenance. Dredge operators earn between three thousand and eight thousand naira per day, while labourers take home between one thousand five hundred and three thousand naira (Aniekan, personal communication, April 16, 2026). The site owner usually takes a cut from every lorry load sold, in addition to paying the crew their daily wages and covering diesel costs.

The sand that is extracted from the Mkpok brook is sharp sand. This variety of sand is formed by the natural weathering and sorting of rock particles in flowing water. Sharp sand is the type most prized by the construction industry for concrete mixing, foundation work, and building block production because its angular particle shape creates stronger bonds in concrete than rounder beach or pit sand (IndexBox, n.d.). At the point of sale directly from the site, sharp sand is priced between four thousand and nine thousand naira (#4,000- #9,000) per tonne. A standard twenty-tonne lorry load therefore sells for between seventy thousand and one hundred and five thousand naira (#70,000- #105,000) from the brook (Aniekan, personal communication, April 16, 2026). Once the tipper lorry transports the sand to different construction places or markets for resell in Uyo or surrounding towns, the selling price rises by a further thirty to fifty per cent to account for transportation costs and market margin, putting the final transaction value of a single lorry load between one hundred thousand and one hundred and fifty thousand naira (#100,000- #150,000) at the point of delivery to a construction buyer (Vanguard, 2010). The buyers of the sand are mostly building contractors, block-making businesses, and private individuals constructing homes or commercial buildings in Uyo and its surrounding urban areas.

Proliferation of Sand Mining in Onna

Between 2005 and 2018, sand mining in Onna Local Government Area shifted from a local economic endeavor into a full-scale extractive operation that overwhelmed the capacity of the Mkpok brook to absorb the damage being inflicted on it. The expansion of this form of unregulated mining was consequent upon the lack of any meaningful enforcement from the government. As a result of this, operators became increasingly confident that the Mkpok brook was an unregulated territory that was ripe for exploitation. Small-scale sand mining had been carried out along the creeks but the introduction of sand dredging machines in the form of suction pumps gave rise to serious environmental concerns.

These dredging activities were consistently carried out without bureaucratic discipline and in sheer disregard of statutory governance. Different miners brought in dredger units as demand from Uyo's

construction sector rose, anchoring them along stretches of the brook that had not previously been touched. By April 2016, the situation was getting seemingly out of hand as the Vanguard news reported that no fewer than thirty-two dredgers were recorded operating simultaneously along the Mkpok brook alone, each working continuously from morning to evening and collectively removing huge volumes of sandy sediment from the streambed (Moses, 2016).

The proliferation of illegal operators during this period had a specific social character that distinguished it from ordinary commercial informality. Investigations revealed that most of the owners of the dredging plants were mostly non-Akwa Ibom from South-Eastern states who bribed community leaders with locally brewed gin, goat meat, and token cash payments to secure access to communal land and waterways (Offong, personal communication, April 19, 2026). The then Commissioner for Works, Mr. Ephraim Inyang-Eyen, confirmed this directly to the Nigerian Voice journalists stating that:

“Believe me; the owners are from neighboring states. Because they cannot do it in Abia, Imo and Anambra states, they just brought those things to come and destroy our environment. And unfortunately, from my findings, they deceived our elders, gave them goats, gave them hot drinks and kola nuts and a little money. And they surrendered (Umo, 2016)...”

This cross-state influx of sand operators meant that Onna was at the receiving end of a regional enforcement problem that its own government had not anticipated nor prepared for. Report on illegal sand mining across the African continent between 1990 and 2021 identified Nigeria as one of six countries where the activity generated not only environmental conflict but also non-violent social conflicts including protests, threats, and community complaints (Aduda & Aduda, 2024). This was a consistent pattern with the youth mobilization that was seen in Onna's Mkpok community during this period.

Figure 3. Sand Dredging Operations along Mkpok Brook in Onna

Source: Uduak Umo, "How Akwa Ibom Elders Gave Our Environment to Non-Indigenes to Destroy in Exchange for 'Kaikai,'" *The Nigerian Voice*, April 8, 2016

Impact of Unregulated Sand Mining in Onna

The most visible impact of the illegal sand mining activities is the damage to the Mkpok brook itself. The continuous removal of sandy sediments from the brook bed over many years has lowered the streambed, destabilized its banks, and widened the channel through accelerated erosion. This is precisely the process that Kondolf described in his work on instream gravel mining, where he found that when the continuity of sediment transport in a water body is interrupted by extraction, the flow becomes sediment-starved and prone to erode the channel bed and banks, producing channel incision, coarsening of bed material, and the systematic loss of aquatic habitat (Kondolf, 1997). In Mkpok brook, this incision reached depths exceeding about twenty (20) metres by April 2016, when the then Commissioner for Works, Mr. Ephraim Inyang-Eyen, confirmed during an on-site inspection that the subsoil beneath the Mkpok bridge had been hollowed out to a depth that made conventional bridge construction impossible (IndexBox, n.d.). He told the Nigerian Voice that :

“I am giving a one-week grace for owners of barges to remove all the dredgers they brought to destroy our environment. As we sit today, we cannot build a bridge at Ekpene Ukpa, we cannot build a bridge at Mkpok; because the entire surface that should hold the bridge has been taken out. Now if you remove the clay, you remove the entire sand that is supposed to hold the column. When you put the column, it floats. Some of these things are damaging our environment. If those things are allowed to continue, our generations, our children will not have where to call their own” (Umo, 2016).

The Mkpok bridge which connects Onna to other places like Etinan through the Ndon Eyo junction developed visible cracks in its columns directly due to this subsoil removal. The spokesman of Mkpok youths Mr. Emayak Sylvanus warned that should the bridge collapse, many communities in Onna would be completely cut off from the rest of the state (Moses, 2016). Mr. Ephraim Inyang-Eyen further added that:

“We cannot sit and watch our state being destroyed. If this bridge collapses now, business and economic activities of the people here would be crippled including mobility in and out of this part of the state (Umo, 2016),”

And then he sent another message to the defaulters saying that:

“Those who own those dredgers should be ready because any moment from now, we’ll go for them and anyone impounded will pay 5 million naira. I have said it before. When I impound it, I lock it up and you cannot take it out. You will go to Ministry of Finance or sub treasury, pay, bring the receipt. We then unlock, and you move the dredger that day. Now that we are announcing, they’re not hearing. You know, people like to dare government; they believe government cannot do anything (Umo, 2016).”

Beyond the bridge, the physical landscape of Onna has been disfigured by borrow pit formations. Some of the lands which are adjacent to the Mkpok brook, where farming activities formally took place have turned into waterlogged excavation craters as dredging expanded outward from the brook's immediate banks. An examination of sand mining environments across Akwa Ibom State confirmed that over eighty (80) hectares of land had been degraded and abandoned across affected LGAs, with no post-mining restoration attempted and no compensation paid to farmers whose land had been destroyed (Abraham et al., 2021). Furthermore, research on the agricultural consequences of sand mining in a comparable West African setting found that mined fields showed severe declines in soil carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and magnesium compared to unmined fields, and that the destruction of food crops came with no compensation payments or land reclamation from either operators or government (Hemmler et al., 2024). The same undercurrents applied to Onna, where farming households lost their productive lands to sand

extraction while bearing the full financial cost of that loss themselves. In an interview conducted with Mrs Iniabasi Effiong, a fifty-four-year-old farmer in Mkpok, who had farmed land close to the Mkpok brook for over two decades before dredging operations rendered it permanently unproductive. She explained that:

Before those dredger people came, I was farming on that land. I planted cassava, I planted cocoyam, I planted vegetables. The land was good. When rain fell, water came and went. It did not stay. But when they started bringing those machines to dig the river, everything changed. The ground near the river started sinking. The water from the river began coming into my farm. It does not go again. It just stays there and kills everything I plant. I have tried to plant three times, and the water always spoil my crops (Effiong, personal communication, April 16, 2026).

Measurable water quality deterioration was also observed at the Mkpok brook as a result of dredging. Sand extraction releases suspended sediment into the water column, raising turbidity levels, reducing dissolved oxygen, and disrupting the chemical balance of the aquatic environment. A study on the physico-chemical effects of sand mining on Ikot Ekpan River found significant seasonal variations in turbidity, sulphate, ammonium, nitrate, and nitrite levels between dredged and undredged sections of the waterway, confirming that dredging activity directly alters the chemical composition of affected water bodies (David, 2019). In the Mkpok brook, where thirty-two dredgers were simultaneously disturbing the streambed, the volume of suspended sediment released into the water during daily operations would be substantial. Communities that drew water from the brook for domestic use and small-scale fishing were therefore exposed to a water source that was increasingly compromised by its own extraction.

Conclusion

This paper has examined the environmental impacts of sand mining in Onna Local Government Area from 1990 to 2024, tracing the causes that drove extraction into the Mkpok brook, the manner in which the extraction expanded, and the physical and ecological consequences it has imposed on the communities of Onna. The activities of unregulated sand mining in Onna is not simply an environmental problem. It is the outcome of the failure of the Nigerian state to enforce its own mining legislations and the failure of community leaders to resist the entry of non-indigene operators. These failures led to the conditions under which thirty-two dredgers could work the Mkpok brook simultaneously, removing over twenty metres of sandy subsoil from beneath a public bridge, converting productive farmland into permanent wastelands, and chemically altering the water quality of a stream on which Onna's communities depended for food and daily use. The communities of Mkpok, Awa, Nung Ndem, and the surrounding Onna settlements paid the full environmental cost of this extraction. The operators, who were largely from outside the state, took the profits and left.

The recommendations that follow from these findings require the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources to enforce the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act of 2007 consistently, not reactively. The current pattern of ministerial visits followed by verbal warnings without durable enforcement must end. Secondly, the state government must establish a dedicated post-mining restoration fund which should be financed through royalties collected from licensed operators, to remediate some degraded sites including the borrow pits and eroded farmlands of Onna. Thirdly, community land rights over waterways must be strengthened so that operators cannot secure access to community brooks through the informal gifting of alcohol and livestock to local elders. Finally, the Akwa Ibom State Government should commission a comprehensive hydrological assessment of the Mkpok brook to determine the current depth of channel incision

and the structural risk still posed to the Mkpok bridge, as the 2016 inspection confirmed the compromise which has not been formally resolved.

References

- Abraham, C. M., Essien, K., Umoh, E. U., Umoh, E. C., & Ehiremem, L. E. (2021). Towards effective monitoring of sand mining sites and post management techniques in sand dredged environment of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Ecology*, 6(1), 094–097. <https://doi.org/10.17352/gje.000024>
- Accio. (n.d.). *Dredger price in Nigeria: 2025 updated rates*. Retrieved April 16, 2026, from <https://www.accio.com/plp/dredger-price-in-nigeria>
- Adebayo, B. (2017). *Shifting sands: Lagos communities count the cost of dredging*. Pulitzer Center. Retrieved April 17, 2026, from <https://pulitzercenter.org/stories/shifting-sands-lagos-communities-count-cost-dredging>
- Aduda, L., & Aduda, L. (2024). The conflict potential of sand: Illegal sand mining on the African continent. *Environment and Security*, 2(4), 548–567. <https://doi.org/10.1163/27727891-bja10043>
- African Land. (n.d.). *The essential guide to dredging services in Nigeria*. Retrieved April 15, 2026, from <https://african.land/blog/article/the-essential-guide-to-dredging-services-in-nigeria>
- Akpan, I. E. (2015). *Sand mining and environmental degradation in Ini LGA, Akwa Ibom State* (Unpublished bachelor's thesis). Department of Geography and Regional Planning, University of Uyo.
- Akpan, S. (2026, April 16). Personal interview, sand miner, Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Akwa Ibom State Government. (n.d.). *About Akwa Ibom*. Retrieved April 14, 2026, from <https://akwaibomstate.gov.ng/about-akwa-ibom/>
- Aliu, I. R., Akoteyon, I. S., & Soladoye, O. (2022). Sustaining urbanization while undermining sustainability: The socio-environmental characterization of coastal sand mining in Lagos, Nigeria. *GeoJournal*, 87(6), 5267–5287. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-021-10501-2>
- Aniekan, U. (2026, April 14). Personal interview, dredger operator, Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. (*Personal communication; not included in APA reference list.*)
- Attah, N. M., Boateng, A. B., & Koranteng, E. (2024). Issues on sustainability of sand mining environment. *ILARD International Journal of Geography and Environmental Management*, 10(10), 67–79.
- David, G. S. (2019). The effect of sand mining on the physico-chemical parameters of Ikot Ekpan River, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Aquatic Science and Marine Biology*, 2(4), 21–27.
- Effiong, I. (2026, April 16). Personal interview, farmer, Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Ehirim, U. G., Awhefeada, U. V., & Abuza, A. E. (2022). Sand dredging activities in the extractive industry in Nigeria: Impact, regulation and remedies. *Commonwealth Law Review Journal*, 8, 458–475.
- Encyclopaedia Britannica. (n.d.). *Akwa Ibom*. Retrieved April 11, 2026, from <https://www.britannica.com/place/Akwa-Ibom>
- Gavriletea, M. D. (2017). Environmental impacts of sand exploitation: Analysis of sand market. *Sustainability*, 9(7), Article 1118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071118>
- Global Forest Watch. (n.d.). *Onna*. Retrieved April 14, 2026, from [Global Forest Watch](#)

- Harry, T. A., Peter, E. J., & Udoduk, N. A. (2022). Environmental impact assessment of oil producing communities in part of the Niger Delta: A case study of Ibeno, Ikot Abasi, Onna and Esit-Eket Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Environmental Contaminants Reviews*, 5(2), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.26480/ecr.02.2022.45.52>
- Hemmler, K. S., Asare, K. Y., Tenkorang, E. Y., & Buerkert, A. (2024). Sand mining deteriorates soil fertility and farming livelihoods around Accra, Ghana. *Scientific Reports*, 14, Article 15131. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-66062-4>
- IndexBox. (n.d.). *Nigeria sand for construction market: Analysis, forecast, size, trends and insights*. Retrieved April 17, 2026, from <https://www.indexbox.io/store/africa-sand-for-construction-market-analysis-forecast-size-trends-and-insights/>
- Kondolf, G. M. (1997). Hungry water: Effects of dams and gravel mining on river channels. *Environmental Management*, 21(4), 533–551. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002679900048>
- Leal Filho, W., Hunt, J., Lingos, A., Platje, J., Vieira, L. W., Will, M., & Gavriletea, M. D. (2021). The unsustainable use of sand: Reporting on a global problem. *Sustainability*, 13(6), Article 3356. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063356>
- Moses, T. (2016, April 12). *Illegal sand mining threatens Calabar–Itu, Mkpok bridges*. *Vanguard*. Retrieved April 17, 2026, from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/>
- Offong, D. (2026, April 19). Personal interview, Clan Head, Mkpok Onna, Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Premium Times. (2020, December 20). *Inside Akwa Ibom communities where sand excavation degrades environment*. Premium Times. Retrieved April 14, 2026, from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/>
- Right for Education. (2024, October 29). *Significance of sand mining in Nigerian communities*. Retrieved April 14, 2026, from <https://rightforeducation.org/2024/10/29/sand-mining-nigerian-communities/>
- Sand business, odd but lucrative*. (2010, October 4). *Vanguard*. Retrieved April 17, 2026, from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/>
- Sand Dredgers. (n.d.). *14-inch sand pumping dredger solutions for Nigeria*. Retrieved April 15, 2026, from <https://www.sanddredgers.com/14-inch-sand-pumping-dredger-in-nigeria/>
- Sand Dredgers. (n.d.). *Main structure and working principle of sand mining dredge*. Retrieved April 15, 2026, from <https://www.sanddredgers.com/main-structure-working-principle-sand-mining-dredge/>
- Sand Pump Machine. (n.d.). *How much does a sand dredge cost?* Retrieved April 16, 2026, from <https://www.sandpumpmachine.com/how-much-does-a-sand-dredge-cost/>
- Torres, A., Brandt, J., Lear, K., & Liu, J. (2017). A looming tragedy of the sand commons. *Science*, 357(6355), 970–971. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao0503>
- Umo, U. (2016, April 8). *How Akwa Ibom elders gave our environment to non-indigenes to destroy in exchange for “Kaikai”*. *The Nigerian Voice*. Retrieved April 14, 2026, from <https://www.thenigerianvoice.com/>
- Umo, U. (2016, April 8). *How Akwa Ibom elders gave our environment to non-indigenes to destroy in exchange for “Kaikai”*. *The Nigerian Voice*. Retrieved April 17, 2026, from <https://www.thenigerianvoice.com/>
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2022). *Sand and sustainability: 10 strategic recommendations to avert a crisis*. UNEP/GRID-Geneva. <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/38362>

